

Synthesis of thiocyanato(pyridine)cobaloximes

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Octahedral cobalt(III) complexes are formed by the aerial oxidation of cobalt(II) salts in the presence of dimethylglyoxime and pyridines. The oximes are bonded as bidentate chelates occupying the planar positions and the complexes have *trans*-octahedral geometry with pyridines and thiocyanate in the axial positions. NMR observation suggests that in solution these compounds exist as mixtures of the neutral species $[\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2(\text{SCN})(\text{L})]$ and the salt $[\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2(\text{SCN})_2]^- [\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2(\text{L})_2]^+$. IR spectra provide the evidence for the coordination of ambidentate thiocyanate group through the S-end.

Cobaloximes are complexes containing the bis(dimethylglyoximate)cobalt(III) moiety¹, $\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2^+$ (DH = mono-anion of dimethylglyoxime). The cobaloximes and their derivatives simulate the reactions of vitamin-B₁₂ and are useful as models² for vitamin-B₁₂. The X-ray crystal structure of alkylcobaloximes³ suggests a higher positive charge on cobalt, thus permitting relatively stronger attachment of either a base or an anion along the axial direction. As a large number of different alkyl groups and bases may be bound to the $\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2^+$ moiety, it was possible to study the influence of steric and electronic effects of the axial ligands on cobaloxime structure and reactivity⁴. Cobaloximes have played its role in helping to understand the reactivity of the cobalt-carbon bond⁵. This paper describes cobalt(III) complexes formed with thiocyanate and pyridines having the general formula $[\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2(\text{SCN})(\text{L})]$ (L = pyridine and 4-substituted-pyridines) with the oxime in the planar positions and the pyridines and anion occupy the extra-planar axial positions.

Results and discussion

Cobalt thiocyanate $\text{Co}(\text{SCN})_2$, dimethylglyoxime DH_2 and the ligand (L) react with in presence of air to form a series of thiocyanato(ligand)cobaloximes, where ligand L = pyridine and 4-substituted-pyridines (Table 1).

The molar conductivities of $\sim 10^{-3}M$ solutions of the complexes in MeOH show that they are non-electrolytes. The absorptions at 240–260 nm have been assigned to intra-ligand $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition of the coordinated dimethylglyoxime⁶. The shoulder at around 300 nm is attributed to the $d\pi(\text{Co}) \rightarrow \pi^*(\text{DH}^-)$ transition⁷. The electronic spectra show a band centered at 420–430 nm due to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$ transition, characteristic of cobalt(III) complexes having an octahedral arrangement⁸. The band at 330–360 nm is at-

Complex $[\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2(\text{SCN})\text{L}]$ where L =	Decomp. temp. °C	Co % : Found (Calcd.)
$\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ (Pyridine)	208	13.14 (13.84)
$\text{H}_2\text{N}-\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}$ (4-Aminopyridine)	195	13.21 (13.37)
$\text{Br}-\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}$ (4-Bromopyridine)	186	11.06 (11.68)
$\text{NC}-\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}$ (4-Cyanopyridine)	175	12.56 (13.08)
$\text{H}_2\text{NOC}-\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}$ (Isonicotinamide)	192	11.92 (12.57)
$\text{H}_3\text{C}_2-\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}$ (4-Ethylpyridine)	178	12.47 (12.99)
$\text{H}_3\text{C}-\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}$ (4-Methylpyridine)	174	13.11 (13.40)
$\text{H}_2\text{C}=\text{HC}-\text{C}_5\text{H}_4\text{N}$ (4-Vinylpyridine)	162	12.53 (13.05)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

tributed to pyridine \rightarrow cobalt transition. The electronic spectrum of $[\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2(\text{SCN})(4\text{-NH}_2\text{Py})]$ gives four transitions at 236 (ϵ 32583), 285 (21000), 352 (11013) and 418 nm (ϵ 2583).

IR spectra of all these complexes show the main bands due to the coordinated dimethylglyoxime, pyridines and the vibrations of ambidentate thiocyanate ligand. The $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ band of the free DH_2 (1620 cm^{-1}) shifted to lower frequencies ($1560\text{--}1570\text{ cm}^{-1}$) due to the coordination. A strong band due to $\nu_{\text{N}-\text{O}}$ of the ionized N–OH group of DH_2 observed in these complexes at $1230\text{--}1245\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and an additional $\nu_{\text{N}-\text{O}}$ band at $1085\text{--}1095\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicate that N–O bonds of the coordinated DH^- are not entirely equivalent⁹. The weak intensity band observed at $1700\text{--}1750\text{ cm}^{-1}$ belongs to the deformation mode of the intramolecular hydrogen bridge, establishing a square-planar structure for the $\text{Co}(\text{DH})_2^+$ moiety¹⁰. The characteristic $\nu_{\text{Co}-\text{N}}$ bands in these complexes are observed at $510\text{--}520$ and 420 cm^{-1} due to Co–N (oxime) and Co–N (base), respectively. The intensity and sharpness of the ν_{CN} band at $2110\text{--}2140\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in these complexes

clearly show Co-S bonding¹¹.

¹H NMR shifts of the complexes show that on coordination, the CH₃ groups of DH₂ at δ 1.98 undergoes a clear downfield shift by about 0.40 ppm and observed at δ 2.35–2.45. The aromatic protons of pyridine ligands in the complexes are observed downfield compared to the free ligands. In case of [Co(DH)₂(SCN)(4-NH₂Py)] complex, the peaks are observed at δ 2.39 (eq. CH₃), 7.50 (C₂, C₆-H), 6.40 (C₃, C₅-H) and 6.15 (NH₂), and the intensity ratio of the peaks is 6 : 1 : 1 : 1. All the other complexes follows the same trend.

The *trans*-structure of the cobaloximes should render the four methyl groups of DH₂ equivalent resulting in only one signal, whereas the *cis*-compound, because of lower symmetry, should give rise to more number of signals¹². In the present case, instead of a single peak for the four CH₃ protons as expected for the *trans*-configuration, either two or three signals are observed, indicating the presence of more than one distinct chemical species in solution. Eventhough the available evidences in solid state favour the formulation as [Co(DH)₂(SCN)(L)], the complexes are (apparently on the basis of NMR evidences) mixtures of the neutral species [Co(DH)₂(SCN)(L)] and the salt [Co(DH)₂(L)₂]⁺[Co(DH)₂(SCN)₂]⁻ in solution. This behavior is very similar to the observation of Hill and Morallee¹³ for [Co(DH)₂(Ph₃P)(CN)] complexes and of Trogler *et al.*¹⁴ for [(*t*-Bupy)Co(DH)₂X] and [(Bu₃P)Co(DH)₂X] complexes and their corresponding ion-pairs. However, we were unable to observe this tendency of salt formation in the corresponding azidocobaloxime complexes with primary amines¹⁵ and pyridines, where clear sharp signals assignable to the neutral species alone were obtained. It has been reported¹⁴ that the ion-pair is formed by the cobalt(II) - catalyzed reactions (Co^{II} present as an impurity in trace amounts before oxidation is complete) of [Co(DH)₂(SCN)(L)] giving the following equilibrium :

which depends markedly on the nature of the solvent and the ligand.

¹³C NMR spectra of these complexes support the conclusion drawn on the basis of ¹H NMR chemical shifts. The oxime CH₃ carbon signal shifts downfield (9.8 to 13.0 ppm). The imine carbon appears at ~154–152 ppm, which is slightly upfield compared to the value of free DH₂ (152.0 ppm)¹⁶. Although a single peak was expected for the ¹³C of the CH₃ groups of Co(DH)₂⁺ moiety, in practice invariably

two or more signals were obtained indicating the presence of more than one distinct chemical species, i.e. the neutral compound and the ion-pair in variable proportions in solution¹². ¹³C NMR signals of the pyridine ligands also undergo downfield shift on complexation.

The thermal decomposition studies indicate that thermal stability of all these cobaloximes is very high and with increase in temperature mass-loss is seen corresponding to polymeric intermediates and the ultimate formation of Co₃O₄ as the end-product.

Experimental

Cobalt(II) nitrate, KSCN, dimethylglyoxime (all B.D.H.), pyridine and substituted pyridines (4-aminopyridine, 4-picoline, 4-ethylpyridine, 4-bromopyridine hydrochloride, 4-cyanopyridine, 4-vinylpyridine and isonicotinamide) (all SD Fine chemicals) were used. An ethanolic solution of Co(NCS)₂ was obtained by the metathetic reaction of Co(NO₃)₂·6H₂O and KSCN, filtering off the precipitated KNO₃ and reducing the volume.

Cobalt content was determined by reported method¹⁷. Microanalyses were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 240C elemental analyzer. IR spectra (KBr) were obtained on a Perkin-Elmer FTIR 1605 instrument and ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra (CDCl₃/DMSO) on a Varian-Gemini 200 spectrometer referenced to TMS. Thermal analysis was performed on a Mettler-Toledo Star system.

Synthesis of complexes :

All the cobalt(III) complexes, [Co(DH)₂(SCN)(L)] (L = pyridines) were synthesized by a common procedure in which air was bubbled for 2–6 h through an ethanolic solution of Co(SCN)₂, dimethylglyoxime and pyridine in 1:2:2 stoichiometric proportions. The mixture was then allowed to stand for 1 h after which the yellow-brown complexes deposited at the bottom were filtered and washed with EtOH followed by Et₂O and finally dried *in vacuo* (yields 60–70%). The reaction presumably proceeds in the following manner :

[Co(DH)₂(SCN)(Py)] : Yield 70%, ν_{max} 2117, 1718, 1560, 1449, 1365, 1238, 1092, 760, 512, 445 cm⁻¹, ¹H NMR δ 2.38 (s, eq. CH₃), 7.42 (m, C₃, C₅-H), 7.90 (m, C₄-H), 8.10 (d, C₂, C₆-H), ¹³C NMR δ 12.98 (eq. CH₃), 129.62 (C₃, C₅), 137.34 (C₄), 151.42 (C=N), 154.42 ppm (C₂, C₆); [Co(DH)₂(SCN)(4-NH₂Py)] : 65%; ν_{max} 2099, 1746, 1557, 1456, 1364, 1240, 1091, 743, 513, 448 cm⁻¹, ¹H NMR δ 2.39 (s, eq. CH₃), 6.40 (d, C₃, C₅-H), 7.50 (d,

C₂, C₆-H), 6.15 (s, NH₂), ¹³C NMR δ 12.78 (eq. CH₃), 118.40 (C₃, C₅), 160.12 (C₄), 149.39 (C=N), 153.85 ppm (C₂, C₆); [Co(DH)₂(SCN)(4-BrPy)] : 62%, ν_{max} 2112, 1701, 1556, 1431, 1364, 1242, 1093, 728, 512, 444 cm⁻¹, ¹H NMR δ 2.36 (s, eq. CH₃), 7.60 (d, C₃, C₅-H), 8.20 (d, C₂, C₆-H), ¹³C NMR δ 13.15 (eq. CH₃), 130.84 (C₃, C₅), 138.34 (C₄), 152.18 (C=N), 153.22 ppm (C₂, C₆); [Co(DH)₂(SCN)(4-CNPy)] : 65%, ν_{max} 2115, 1725, 1559, 1425, 1374, 1243, 1094, 743, 514, 449 cm⁻¹, ¹H NMR δ 2.39 (s, eq. CH₃), 7.90 (d, C₃, C₅-H), 8.80 (d, C₂, C₆-H), ¹³C NMR δ 13.39 (eq. CH₃), 131.20 (C₃, C₅), 151.342 (C₄), 152.65 (C=N), 155.65 (C₂, C₆), 145.58 ppm (CN); [Co(DH)₂(SCN)(4-CONH₂Py)] : 2117, 1701, 1557, 1427, 1396, 1239, 1094, 765, 513, 451 cm⁻¹, ¹H NMR δ 2.36 (s, eq. CH₃), 7.70 (d, C₃, C₅-H), 8.35 (d, C₂, C₆-H), 8.80 ppm (s, CONH₂), ¹³C NMR δ 13.28 (eq. CH₃), 128.63 (C₃, C₅), 148.60 (C₄), 151.59 (C=N), 155.46 (C₂, C₆), 168.20 ppm (CONH₂); [Co(DH)₂(SCN)(4-EtPy)] : 68% ν_{max} 2108, 1710, 1558, 1445, 1366, 1240, 1094, 743, 516, 448 cm⁻¹, ¹H NMR δ 2.40 (s, eq. CH₃), 6.95 (d, C₃, C₅-H), 7.92 (d, C₂, C₆-H), 3.20 (q, CH₂), 1.90 ppm (t, CH₃), ¹³C NMR δ 12.94 (eq. CH₃), 126.92 (C₃, C₅), 155.42 (C₄), 150.25 (C=N), 152.16 (C₂, C₆), 27.35 (CH₂), 13.64 ppm (CH₃); [Co(DH)₂(SCN)(4-MePy)] : 66%, ν_{max} 2113, 1715, 1559, 1448, 1362, 1239, 1093, 745, 514, 447 cm⁻¹, ¹H NMR δ 2.44 (s, eq. CH₃), 7.40 (d, C₃, C₅-H), 8.00 (d, C₂, C₆-H), 3.90 ppm (s, CH₃), ¹³C NMR δ 13.05 (eq. CH₃), 128.40 (C₃, C₅), 156.05 (C₄), 150.84 (C=N), 152.48 (C₂, C₆), 22.50 ppm (CH₃); [Co(DH)₂(SCN)(4-VinylPy)] : 61%, ν_{max} 2118, 1721, 1556, 1440, 1358, 1240, 1093, 740, 514, 449 cm⁻¹, ¹H NMR δ 2.38 (s, eq. CH₃), 7.30 (d, C₃, C₅-H), 8.20 (d, C₂, C₆-H), 2.80 (d, CH₂), 1.60 ppm (t, CH), ¹³C NMR δ 13.24 (eq. CH₃), 129.56 (C₃, C₅), 153.86 (C₄), 151.25 (C=N), 155.26 (C₂, C₆), 134.30 (CH), 119.40 ppm (CH₂).

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